

Researching BLENDER

Blender Learning Experiences in a Network of Distributed Environments and Resources

by Nelson Gonçalves [aka nafergo]

Blender Conference 2010
29-30-31 october
Amsterdam

Libre Software at “my” schools

What?

- What "blenderheads" do to create the culture in which they live, how the **architecture of participation of the community** is constructed.
- Studying the culture of "blenderheads" and produce a detailed description of **how people learn Blender**.

How?

- **Theoretical framework:** Situated Cognition (Brown, Collins & Duguid, 1989), Communities of Practice (Lave & Wenger, 1991), Connectivism (Siemens, 2005), Personal Learning Environment (Attwell, 2007) and Actor-Network Theory (Law, 1992).
- **Methodology:** Ethnography (Gregory, 2005).

How?

Personal Learning Env

Community is growing, engaged and dynamic

Forums: registered members

Forums: discussion activities

	Posts p/ Day		Topics p/ Day		Posts p/ Topic	
	May-08	Oct-10	May-08	Oct-10	May-08	Oct-10
Blender Artists	465.8	523.0	51.0	58.8	9.1	8.9
Blend.Polis	116.2	125.7	8.8	10.7	13.2	11.8
The Blender Clan	94.8	129.8	7.5	10.3	12.7	12.6
Blender3D.cz	33.9	22.2	2.9	2.1	11.5	10.6
Blender.it	55.6	52.2	6.1	5.9	9.0	8.8
Polska Strona Blendera	19.2	13.2	2.5	1.8	7.6	7.5
G-Blender	9.0	6.7	2.2	1.6	4.1	4.3
Blenderownia	52.2	53.7	4.8	4.4	10.9	12.3
Blender Brasil	21.8	24.6	4.0	2.9	5.5	8.4
Blender PT	2.8	4.5	0.4	0.3	7.2	13.1
Blender Underground	27.3	42.8	2.4	4.1	11.2	10.5
BlenderNewbies	13.6	27.3	2.3	3.6	5.9	7.5
Pinoy Blender User Group	2.7	7.4	0.9	2.3	3.2	3.2

Open movies presales

- S
- ED+BBB+S
- BBB
- ED

Starting a snowball...

- People listed in Blender Conference proceedings: 2004-2010
- People listed in movie credits (movie): Elephants Dream, Big Buck Bunny & Sintel
- Blender Foundation Certified Trainer list and BFCT Board
- Let's combine this data...

- People listed in Open movies credits
- Movie ties excluded from it's own network
- There's a tie between 2 individuals if they share an affiliation (i.e. Blender Conference, other movies credits or BFCT)

Total nodes	52	31	121
Total links	350	414	598
Density	0.13198	0.44516	0.04118

Degree Centrality

- The number of ties that a node has.
- More central nodes will be positioned closer to the centre of the canvas.
- The degree is a measure of the 'activity' of the node.

Betweenness

- The extent to which a node lies between other nodes in the network.
- More central nodes will be positioned closer to the centre of the canvas.

Why?

To inform strategies to...

- Increase quantity, quality and diversity of Blender learning
- Develop an ecosystem of resources to support user learning progress
- Increase user base
- Understand new learning experiences
- Develop better ways to support learning
- Find solutions to: academic inflation, lifelong learning, innovation, “long tail”, etc.

Thank you for listening

- nafergo@gmail.com
- <http://nafergo.intervir.net>